

NDAC/LO/074

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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, III.

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1. Introduction

In a continuing series of investigations, the present paper deals mainly with the short-period binaries with curved motion over 2.5 years. These may be schematically divided into three groups. For known binaries of short (<30 years) period, some orbital elements will be known, and the HIPPARCOS observations may be used to improve others, mainly the separations and (possibly) the mass-ratio. This requires "individual" methods, and will be the subject of a future study. The second group consists of the resolved binaries (discovered by the methods of NDAC/LO/071), where we will study here the increased errors due to orbital curvature. The third group, finally, is the astrometric pairs. These were discussed before in NDAC/LO/039, but we may now be more specific on some points.

2. Simulated binary motion

Instead of the linear approximation used before, the present version of SAMP takes real (Thiele-Innes) binary orbital elements as input, and computes (at each FOV) the true positions in the orbit. The binary is specified by the apparent magnitudes for the components, the (mean) angular separation and the orbital period, while the geometry (A,B,F,G), phase (T) and eccentricity are randomized. With simple "main-sequence" mass-luminosity and mass-colour relations, the period and angular separations determine the component masses and colours, and also the distance to the system. The barycentric proper motion components are derived from an assumed 20 km/s (random direction) space velocity.

The simulated observations are fully realistic. The "old" (linear) solution-program is still used in the analysis, however, and in order to compare the solution parameters with the true ones, each binary is

characterized by a set of linear elements (= positions and proper motions for each component). These elements should ideally be straight-line LS-fits to the true curved orbital arcs, but a simplified conversion has generally been used. For periods above some 5 years, the position of each component at the beginning (P_1), middle (P_2) and end (P_3) of the 2.5 mission is calculated exactly. The proper motion is then given simply by the vector P_1P_3 , and the perpendicular distance from P_2 to P_1P_3 , called s , is a measure of the curvature. The mean position (P) is taken at $1/3 s$ from P_2 towards P_1P_3 , which may be translated into the following formulae:

$$\begin{aligned} x(P) &= ((1-f)x_1 + 2x_2 + fx_3)/3 \\ y(P) &= ((1-f)y_1 + 2y_2 + fy_3)/3 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where

$$f = ((x_2-x_1)(x_3-x_1)+(y_2-y_1)(y_3-y_1))/((x_3-x_1)**2+(y_3-y_1)**2) \quad (2)$$

and where the coordinates of P_k are (x_k, y_k) . A minor complication is that the above definition applied to the total (barycentric+orbital) motion of each component gives a photocentric P different from the photocentre of $P(\text{pr})$ and $P(\text{sec})$. In practice, I define s and the proper motions from the total motions, but the $P:s$ from the orbital motion only. (The mean photocentre is then equal to the photocentre of the mean $P:s$.)

For periods shorter than 2.5 years, an even simpler method is used to derive the mean elements. The proper motions are now given by the barycentric ones, and the mean positions are simply the arithmetic means of a large number of (time-equidistant) orbital positions. A measure of curvature, s' , is obtained from the rms difference between the individual and mean positions. As intuitively apparent, s' is closely related to the semi-major axis; the mean relation is $s' \approx 0.7a$.

3. Resolved binaries

The object of the present tests is to study appreciably curved motions (large s). Therefore, only short periods were tried for some "standard" (8.5 mag primary) systems, as shown in Table 1. These period-distributions are of

course not realistic (cf. Sect. 5), but they gave a number of (large-s)-solutions that could be studied statistically.

Table 1. Typical runs for resolved binaries.

Δm	Sep (")	Per (years)
0.0	0.10	6-30
0.0	0.15	8-30
0.0	0.25	10-30
1.5	0.15	10-30
1.5	0.25	10-30
3.0	0.25	10-30

As expected, for too large s-values, no solutions were obtained. In many such cases, the LS-iterations do converge, but the solution is rejected by the χ^2 -limit $S_{\text{rej}} = 5674$ (for nob=4704, cf. NDAC/LO/071). Roughly, $S < S_{\text{rej}}$ corresponds to $s < 30-40$ mas, and the accepted solutions have then smaller curvatures.

Plots of the standard astrometric rms-errors vs the curvature (s) show a general increase with s. There are deviating values at small s, however, mostly for cases with rapidly varying separation. Neglecting such deviations, the simple mean relation

$$\text{rms} = (\text{rms}_0^2 + (0.13s)^2)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

fits all primary components. The ratios $\text{rms}(\text{sec})/\text{rms}(\text{pr})$ are approximately constant, but rather diminishing with s for $\Delta m = 3$. For the photocentric solutions, eq.(3) is still valid, with s for the photocentre. (For equal-magnitude systems $s(\text{photocentre}) = 0$, and the astrometric errors are almost unaffected by large orbital curvatures. For this case, the photocentric solutions are effectively indistinguishable from "single-star" solutions, although the single-star S-values may be very large.)

The factor 0.13 in eq. (3) is surprisingly large. As derived in NDAC/LO/039, the extra "abscissa-variance" should be about $(0.21s)^2$, and the mean astrometric error-increase (for this position on the sky) would then be only about $(0.034s)^2$. The large discrepancy may be due partially to the simplified derivation in NDAC/LO/039, partly to the systematic nature of the curvature-effects. For the present, we take eq. (3) to be realistic.

The relation (3) may only be obtained from simulated data, in the real reductions we do not know the s -values. We do know the fit to the observations, as given by the χ^2 -measure S . Plots of $\text{rms}(\text{astr})$ vs S are again very illuminating. For all six series of runs, there is a definite limit at about $S_1=5000$ ($=\text{nobs}+3\sigma$). There are large rms-values with small S , but practically no small rms-values for $S>S_1$. This amounts to saying that we should accept as "definitive" only the solutions with $S<S_1$. A "test-zone" may be defined between S_1 and S_2 ($=\text{nobs}+20\sigma$), where adequately converged solutions may still be found. Procedures have to be defined in order to check the cause of the large S as they may equally well be "false" solutions for "linear" systems (cf. NDAC/LO/071).

4. Astrometric binaries

The above conclusions refer to resolved binaries, i.e. systems where a sensible binary solution is obtained. There will also be a lot of closer systems which will be effectively observed as single stars. If the orbital motion is "linear", these will not be distinguishable from single stars, but the question (addressed in NDAC/LO/039) is how the solution is affected by sensible curvature. This has been tested in a number of runs with $\text{Sep}=0''.02-0''.06$, $\Delta m=1.5-3.0$, $\text{Per}=4-25$ years.

As expected, the results are similar to those for resolved binaries. The (single-star) astrometric errors increase with s (for the photocentre), and the lower envelope of the relation conforms to eq. (3). There are more large rms-values at a given s , but this may be due simply to the shorter periods that make a linear fit to the elements less adequate. The plot of rms against χ^2 gives the same S_1 -limit around 5000; the astrometric errors are always large for $S>S_1$. (Although it is not possible to make a sharp borderline, this S -limit corresponds to curvature-values around $s=10-15\text{mas}$.)

Some runs have also been made for even closer systems, with $P<2$ years. The curvature-parameter is now the (differently defined) s' , and it is interesting to derive the analogue to eq. (3) for this case. The data are rather noisy, but

$$\text{rms} = ((0.5)^2 + (0.25s')^2)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

seems to be a reasonable formula. (Again, the S_1 rejection-limit is suitable, corresponding now to $s' \approx 10$ mas).

Another question touched upon in NDAC/LO/039 is the problem with the parallax-determination for binaries with $P \approx 1$ year. In order to test this rather thoroughly, 40 astrometric pairs were created at each of the periods 0.8, 0.9, .. 1.2 years. For the positions and proper motions, results close to eq. (4) were obtained (they were in fact used to derive it). For the parallaxes, however, the error increases more rapidly with s' (or $a(\text{photo-centre})$). A simple linear fit to $a(\text{pc})$ gives the obvious trend with the period shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Slope of the mean relation between parallax error and semi-major axis for the photocentre.

Per (yrs)	slope
<<1 or >>1	0.19
0.8	0.34
0.9	0.79
1.0	0.87
1.1	0.66
1.2	0.4:

The effect is a kind of "resonance" between the expected parallactic displacement and the actual motion of the photocentre. The width of the resonance is plausible, but the important thing to note is that the "extra" parallax-error is only about 0.7 $a(\text{pc})$ even at $P=1$ year. Since (at $P \approx 1$ yr, $\Sigma \leq 5$) $a(\text{tot}) \leq 1.7 \pi$, and $a(\text{pc}) \leq 0.35 a(\text{tot})$, the extra parallax error will seldom exceed 40%. Contrary thus to the statements in NDAC/LO/039, the systems with $P \approx 1$ year will not have grossly erroneous parallaxes.

5. Conclusions

The number of resolved binaries with short periods is expected to be small. Starting from the estimates in NDAC/LO/039, one may give the (crude!) data in Table 3.

Table 3. Percentage of resolved binaries with the curvature parameter s greater than 10 or 25 mas.

Sep(")	$s > 10 \text{ mas}$	$s > 25 \text{ mas}$
0.10	6%	3%
0.15	2%	1%
0.25	0.5%	0.2%

Only for the very closest pairs there will be some with appreciable s -values, and as seen from eq. (3), most of them will still give reasonable astrometric results. (This is even more true if photocentric solutions are considered, the s -values being correspondingly smaller). The few (tens?) problem stars will have large χ^2 -values and may be flagged accordingly.

For the astrometric pairs, a rapid orbital motion is disclosed by a large S -value. For the present "long-period" ($P > 5^y$) runs, the χ^2 -limit $S > S_1$ corresponds to $s > 10$ -15 mas. In NDAC/LO/039, two bad estimates cancel to give a limit very close to this. For the "short-period" runs, we have now $s'_{\text{lim}} \approx 10$ mas. In NDAC/LO/039, $s'_{\text{lim}} = 4.2$ mas was assumed, thus fewer such systems than assumed there will be discovered. It is difficult to give a definite figure, but it seems clear that at most a few hundred astrometric pairs will be discovered. The problems for the parallax for astrometric binaries with periods close to 1 year are also less than anticipated.

In conclusion, we may say that the problems due to binary orbital motion during the 2.5 year lifetime of HIPPARCOS seem to be rather minor.